

Ball as radiator - vertical circle as receiver

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We view one extended radiator. The radiating ball has the radius R . r is the radius of the receiving circle.
 $l =$ distance midpoint of the ball - midpoint of the circle

Fig.1

$$l > R$$

The ball has the luminous intensity I and the surface luminous intensity density $w = \frac{I}{4\pi R^2}$.

We consider, that I is measured in candela and w in candela/m². The medium (pure air) is in whole room with the absorption coefficient m . The density of the medium is constant which means m is constant.

We search the luminous flux through the circle.

$a =$ minimum radius, that is still attained with the angle α .

With figure 1 we recognize at once:

$$a(\alpha) = R \sin \alpha - \frac{l - R \cos \alpha}{\tan \alpha} \quad \tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = \frac{1}{\tan \alpha} \quad (1)$$

More difficult is the calculation from α in dependence of a .
 The transformation of (1) to α is too complicated.
 But it is valid see fig.1:

$$\frac{R}{x+l} = \sin(90^\circ - \alpha) = \cos \alpha \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{a}{x} = \tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = \frac{1}{\tan \alpha} \quad (3)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \tan \alpha = \frac{x}{a} \quad \text{it is valid:} \quad \cos^2 \alpha = \frac{1}{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{R}{x+l} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{x^2}{a^2}}}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{R}{a} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 + x^2} = x + l$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{R^2}{a^2} \cdot (a^2 + x^2) = x^2 + 2lx + l^2$$

$$\Leftrightarrow R^2 - l^2 = x^2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R^2}{a^2}\right) + 2lx$$

$$\Leftrightarrow x^2 + \frac{2lx}{1 - \frac{R^2}{a^2}} = \frac{R^2 - l^2}{1 - \frac{R^2}{a^2}}$$

This is a quadratic equation in x .

$$\Leftrightarrow x^2 + \frac{2la^2x}{a^2 - R^2} = \frac{(R^2 - l^2) \cdot a^2}{a^2 - R^2}$$

With the p-q formula of the normed form:

$$x(a) = \pm \sqrt{\frac{a^2(R^2 - l^2)}{a^2 - R^2} + \left(\frac{la^2}{a^2 - R^2}\right)^2} - \frac{la^2}{a^2 - R^2} \quad (4)$$

because of $x \geq 0$ see fig.1

With (2) and (3) follows:

$$\cos \alpha(a) = \frac{R}{l + x(a)} \quad \text{or} \quad \tan \alpha(a) = \frac{x(a)}{a} \quad (5)$$

For the luminous flux through one inclined circle it is valid see Schröer [2] formula (7):

$$\Phi = 2Ir \cdot \int_{-R}^R \int_0^{\sqrt{R^2 - x_2^2}} \frac{e^{-m\sqrt{(r_1+x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2}}}{((r_1+x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + r^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} dx_1 dx_2 \quad (6)$$

Now we enter to the searched luminous flux:

We integrate in dependence of α in circular arcs on the ball's surface.

Now it is at first $R \geq r$.

Then the light attains the whole circle because of the tangent plane of the ball from 0 till to the angle α_1 . This looks from these points as an inclined circle.

From α_1 till to the angle $\alpha_{max} \leq 90^\circ$ from a single point only an inclined circular segment is lighted (because of the tangent plane). The multiplier of the circular arc is $2\pi R \sin \alpha$. Besides one R (root of the Gram determinant of the metric tensor) is added. To searched luminous flux it is valid, see fig. 1:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & 2wR \cdot \int_0^{\alpha_1} 2\pi R \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^r \int_0^{\sqrt{r^2-x_2^2}} f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) dx_1 dx_2 d\alpha \\ & + 2wR \cdot \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_{max}} 2\pi R \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^{-a(\alpha)} \int_0^{\sqrt{r^2-x_2^2}} f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) dx_1 dx_2 d\alpha \quad (7) \\ & a \in [-r, r] \end{aligned}$$

$b(\alpha) = l - R \cos \alpha$ is the distance that is inserted for r in formula (6). This distance is dependent from α .

$$f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) = \frac{e^{-m\sqrt{(k(\alpha)+x_2)^2+x_1^2+b(\alpha)^2}}}{[(k(\alpha)+x_2)^2+x_1^2+b(\alpha)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (8)$$

$k(\alpha) = R \cdot \sin \alpha$ is inserted for r_1 of formula (6).

At first (7) is valid only for $R \geq r$.

At $R \leq r$ must be still shown, after this we determine α_{max} and α_1 .

The case $R \leq r$ ($\alpha \geq 90^\circ$):

Fig.2

The relation follows:

$$a(\alpha) = R \cdot \cos(\alpha - 90^\circ) + (l - R \cos \alpha) \cdot \tan(\alpha - 90^\circ)$$

$$\cos(-\alpha) = \cos \alpha \quad \tan(-\alpha) = -\tan \alpha$$

$$\Rightarrow \cos(\alpha - 90^\circ) = \cos(90^\circ - \alpha) = \sin \alpha$$

$$\tan(\alpha - 90^\circ) = -\tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = \frac{-1}{\tan \alpha}$$

$$\Rightarrow a(\alpha) = R \sin \alpha - \frac{l - R \cos \alpha}{\tan \alpha} \quad (9)$$

hence the same relation as in the case $0 \leq \alpha \leq 90^\circ$

see (1)

Now we show a second possibility:

Fig.3

It is possible see fig.:

$$a(\alpha) = \frac{R}{\cos(\alpha - 90^\circ)} + l \cdot \tan(\alpha - 90^\circ)$$

$$\cos(\alpha - 90^\circ) = \cos(90^\circ - \alpha) = \sin \alpha$$

$$\tan(\alpha - 90^\circ) = -\tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = \frac{-1}{\tan \alpha}$$

$$\Rightarrow a(\alpha) = \frac{R}{\sin \alpha} - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha}$$

(10)

We must prove that (10) is the same as (9) respectively (1).

$\stackrel{!}{=}$: means: shall equal with

$$\frac{R}{\sin \alpha} - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha} \stackrel{!}{=} R \sin \alpha - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha} + \frac{R \cos \alpha}{\tan \alpha}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\sin \alpha} \stackrel{!}{=} \sin \alpha + \frac{\cos \alpha}{\tan \alpha}$$

Now we introduce notations at the right-angled triangle:

Fig.4

$$\begin{aligned} \sin \alpha &= \frac{q}{s} & \cos \alpha &= \pm \frac{p}{s} & \tan \alpha &= \pm \frac{q}{p} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{s}{q} &\stackrel{!}{=} \frac{q}{s} + \frac{p^2}{sq} & \Leftrightarrow \frac{s}{q} &\stackrel{!}{=} \frac{q^2 + p^2}{sq} = \frac{s^2}{sq} = \frac{s}{q} \end{aligned}$$

Thus (9) and (10) are equal for $0 \leq \alpha \leq 180^\circ$.

It is valid:

$$a(\alpha) = \frac{R}{\sin \alpha} - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \alpha \leq 180^\circ \quad (11)$$

Now we transform to α :

$$\begin{aligned} \sin^2 \alpha &= \frac{\tan^2 \alpha}{1 + \tan^2 \alpha} \\ \Rightarrow a &= \frac{\sqrt{1 + \tan^2 \alpha}}{\tan \alpha} \cdot R - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha} \\ \Rightarrow (a \tan \alpha + l)^2 &= R^2 \cdot (1 + \tan^2 \alpha) \\ \Leftrightarrow a^2 \tan^2 \alpha + 2la \tan \alpha + l^2 &= R^2 + R^2 \tan^2 \alpha \\ \Leftrightarrow \tan^2 \alpha + \frac{2la \tan \alpha}{a^2 - R^2} &= \frac{R^2 - l^2}{a^2 - R^2} \end{aligned}$$

This is a quadratic equation in normed form.

With the p-q-formula:

$$\tan \alpha_{1,2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{R^2 - l^2}{a^2 - R^2} + \left(\frac{la}{a^2 - R^2}\right)^2} - \frac{la}{a^2 - R^2} \quad (12)$$

This is equal to (4) and (5).

The equations (1),(9),(10),(11) are valid for $-R \leq a(\alpha) \leq 0$, too
 We can recognize this with the following figures:

Fig.5

$$\frac{a(\alpha)}{x} = \tan(90^\circ - \alpha) \quad \frac{x}{a(\alpha)} = \tan \alpha$$

$$\frac{R}{l+x} = \cos \alpha = \sin(90^\circ - \alpha)$$

accordance with (2),(3) and (5)

Fig.6

$$a(\alpha) = \frac{R}{\cos(90^\circ - \alpha)} - l \cdot \tan(90^\circ - \alpha) = \frac{R}{\sin \alpha} - \frac{l}{\tan \alpha}$$

That means equality to (11)

determination of α_1 :

It must be $a(\alpha_1) = -r$

determination of α_{max} :

$a(\alpha_{max}) = +r$

In both cases solving to (4) and (5) or (12) to α

We formulate formula (7) once again with $I = 4\pi R^2 \cdot w$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & I \cdot \int_0^{\alpha_1} \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^r \int_0^{\sqrt{r^2-x_2^2}} f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) dx_1 dx_2 d\alpha \\ & + I \cdot \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_{max}} \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^{-a(\alpha)} \int_0^{\sqrt{r^2-x_2^2}} f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) dx_1 dx_2 d\alpha \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} b(\alpha) &= l - R \cos \alpha & k(\alpha) &= R \cdot \sin \alpha \\ f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) &= \frac{e^{-m \sqrt{(k(\alpha)+x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + b(\alpha)^2}}}{[(k(\alpha) + x_2)^2 + x_1^2 + b(\alpha)^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ a(\alpha_1) &= -r & a(\alpha_{max}) &= +r & l &> R \end{aligned}$$

with the use of (4) and (5) or (12)

This formula is valid for $r \leq R$ and $r \geq R$.

In the equations (7) and (13) there are two Gram determinants.

The Gram determinant g_e of the inclined circle is 1.

The Gram determinant's root of the ball is $\sqrt{g_e} = R$.

We cannot transform the formula (13) to an 2-dimensional integral. With numerical methods the calculation is also difficult. Only the Monte-Carlo-method (a stochastically method) is left remaining.

Now we set in (13) $m = 0$ which means the whole room is a vacuum, then the integration with x_1 is possible.

Then it is:

$$f(x_1, x_2, \alpha) = \frac{1}{(x_1^2 + c)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

$$\text{with } c = (k(\alpha) + x_2)^2 + b(\alpha)^2$$

See Gröbner [1] p.39 Nr.20b) section 231:

$$\int_0^{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}} \frac{dx_1}{(x_1^2 + c)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \left[\frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{x_1}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + c}} \right]_0^{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}} \quad (14)$$

control:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dx_1} \left(\frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{x_1}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + c}} \right) &= \frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{\sqrt{x_1^2 + c} - x_1 \cdot \frac{x_1}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + c}}}{x_1^2 + c} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{c + x_1^2 - x_1^2}{\sqrt{x_1^2 + c} \cdot (x_1^2 + c)} = \frac{1}{(x_1^2 + c)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \end{aligned}$$

Thus with (14):

$$\int_0^{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}} \frac{dx_1}{(x_1^2 + c)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}}{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2 + c}}$$

For the luminous flux through the circular disk follows with (13):

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= I \cdot \int_0^{\alpha_1} \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^r \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}}{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2 + c}} dx_2 d\alpha \\ &+ I \cdot \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_{max}} \sin \alpha b(\alpha) \cdot \int_{-r}^{-a(\alpha)} \frac{1}{c} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2}}{\sqrt{r^2 - x_2^2 + c}} dx_2 d\alpha \quad (15) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{with } c = (k(\alpha) + x_2)^2 + b(\alpha)^2$$

$$b(\alpha) = l - R \cos \alpha \quad k(\alpha) = R \cdot \sin \alpha$$

$$a(\alpha_1) = -r \quad a(\alpha_{max}) = +r \quad l > R$$

This 2-dimensional integral can be calculated numerically, the Monte-Carlo-method can be used, too.

At last we derive one approximation formula for $R, r \ll l$. The medium (pure air) is in whole room. The absorption coefficient m is constant [constant density].

The illumination E can be written:

$$E \approx \frac{w}{l^2} \cdot \pi R^2 \cdot e^{-ml} \quad (16)$$

We obtain for the luminous flux:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi \approx E \cdot \pi r^2 &\approx \frac{w \pi^2 R^2 r^2 \cdot e^{-ml}}{l^2} && \text{if } I = 4\pi R^2 \cdot w \\ \Rightarrow \Phi &\approx \frac{I \pi r^2}{4 \cdot l^2} \cdot e^{-ml} && R, r \ll l \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

References

- [1] Wolfgang Gröbner und Nikolaus Hofreiter "Integraltafel Erster Teil" 5.edition 1975 Springer Verlag Vienna
- [2] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux through the inclined circle" Zenodo 2015
- [3] Harald Schröer "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001